

SOME PERSPECTIVES ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF LINGUISTIC SKILLS IN FUTURE TEACHERS

Xamrayeva Umida Farxodovna

Teacher of Foreign Language Faculty

Jizzakh State Pedagogical Institute

hamrayeva@japi.uz

Abstract: This article focuses on developing the linguistic competencies of future English instructors. Linguistic competence is often viewed as an idealized concept that represents the collective knowledge of communication. Community in the form of an ideal speaker-listener. The fundamental concept is an individual's proficiency in a specific language.

Keywords: reforms, standards, linguistic competency, modernization, civilization, competence, communicative competencies, the Common European Framework of Reference (CEFR), and integration.

After attaining independence, Uzbekistan was acknowledged by developed countries and the world community for its socioeconomic, political, and spiritual development. The country's import and export potential has increased significantly, and modern equipment and technology are widely used in industry, manufacturing, agriculture, and other sectors. Gradual education reforms have resulted in the "Uzbek model" that is known globally. We have accelerated program development, provided English language instruction, and published literature, television, newspapers, and electronic magazines. We also introduced remote education and the Republican Scientific and Practical. The center provides methodological support to English language teachers through organization and intensified work to achieve high-quality professional development. Modernizing foreign language instruction in Uzbekistan, particularly English, is projected to have beneficial effects, including a more innovative and effective training approach. Competent teachers have been created in response to societal demand. A social partnership has been established to prepare children to be modern thinkers, communicate freely with people of different nationalities, apply world science to society's development, and train competitive teachers in the global labor market. The goal is to improve education quality by ensuring that future English instructors have C1 competence. In the years of independence, The school system was improved to meet modern standards, including educating foreign language teachers with international qualifications. Comprehensive education reforms have resulted in a nationwide framework for preparing future foreign language teachers based on international best practices. Accelerating

communicative competency development is crucial for increasing the quality of foreign language teacher training. Developing social communication skills in prospective English teachers, providing socio-linguistic training, and establishing their professional profile are crucial for both science and practice. Research aims to improve the competency of future foreign language instructors in the following main areas: Improving the pedagogical approach to preparing foreign language instructors in line with our focus is on meeting worldwide European CEFR criteria, inventing novel technology for future foreign language teachers, and coordinating independent learning both within and outside the classrooms. Scholars have studied the competency formation of foreign language teachers, but there is a lack of research on improving the competence formation of future English language teachers to meet international educational standards. Linguistic competency involves using language to convey and interpret concepts, thoughts, feelings, facts, and views during oral and written exchanges. Such interactions may occur in Language properties, such as grammar, pragmatics, and sociolinguistics, vary depending on social and cultural settings. Linguistic and communication competences are closely linked and often considered equal. Linguistic skill is crucial for effective scientific communication and production. Writing skills include effective language use and content structure, as well as the ability to read and write scientific documents in the reader's language. The ability to read, write, and translate texts into non-native languages, especially commonly used ones, does not necessarily imply comprehensive competency in the language. However, it must be sufficient for reading and understanding. Discussing teachers' linguistic proficiency is crucial as they are responsible for designing, implementing, and developing the syllabus. Language allows people to communicate their thoughts, ideas, and attitudes to others. Linguists now acknowledge the significance of language in identity formation. Language helps us express our identity and interact with others. Successful language learning requires a focus on 'competence'. Listening, speaking, reading, and writing are crucial language abilities for effective communication in everyday life. The future's professional competence level English teachers must possess the ability to understand and interpret linguistic signals, correct pronunciation, memorize new words, communicate freely in a dialogic or monologue manner, prepare presentations, express themselves fluently, understand societal requirements, have scientific-theoretical knowledge of professional competence norms, understand the essence, translate effectively, and implement information. Globalization necessitates training teachers who adhere to international educational standards and possess modern, competitive, and inventive thinking skills. To train qualified foreign language instructors, the government must establish and implement a legal framework that meets modern standards. To ensure the quality and efficacy of future foreign language teachers, especially English, it is

important to focus on developing scientific, theoretical, and practical competencies. Developing professional competence in future English teachers involves identifying and applying competence criteria, pedagogical principles, competency indicators, innovative educational methods, tools, and didactic factors.

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